

ASSESSING UNCERTAINTY CASCADES IN ENERGY AND ENVIRONMENTAL MODELLING: A CASE FOR PORTUGAL

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KEYWORDS

Postnormal science, sustainability assessment, sensitivity auditing

ABSTRACT

In the SEEDS project, we used the energy system optimization framework Calliope to model 271 suboptimal configurations for Portugal's energy transition to 2050 with a Modelling for Generating Alternatives (MGA) perspective. The environmental impacts of these scenarios were then analyzed with the ENBIOS tool, which integrates Life Cycle Assessment and socio-ecosystem metabolism. In this paper, we assess the robustness of our workflow through: (i) Spearman correlation values to address the influence of technologies in two impact categories and (ii) Monte Carlo analysis to compare the uncertainty of Life Cycle Inventories to the option space given by MGA. This process highlighted uncertainty hotspots related to the modelling and indicator choices, as well as the accuracy and reliability of the technology data used. Our results highlight a range of sensitivities among different energy pathways, with open-field solar electricity production, pumped hydro, and electrolysis showing high sensitivity, while wind onshore and biofuel to methane exhibit negative correlations. Monte Carlo simulations show significant uncertainty in the water consumption potential of a single energy system configuration. Transparency and open communication of uncertainty is vital in policymaking to empower stakeholders with necessary information for informed decisions.

INTRODUCTION

Post-normal science (PNS) (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1993) acknowledges the limitations of existing knowledge and the existence of values and stakes and highlights the importance of embracing uncertainty in modelling and decision-making. The SEEDS project objective is to engage citizens in the debate of possible futures of the energy system through a web app (“SEEDS: Stakeholder-Based Environmentally-Sustainable and Economically Doable Scenarios for the Energy Transition,” n.d.). In doing so, it follows the premise of PNS and acknowledges the existence of values and stake, fostering participation to handle them. The two quantitative tools used in the SEEDS project (Calliope for

energy modelling and ENBIOS for environmental assessment) are supported by and used for participatory processes for exploring possible configurations of the renewable energy system in Portugal by different stakeholders.

In this paper we dig deeper into the quantitative analysis of the uncertainty. We assess the cascade of uncertainty and quantify the sensitivity of technological structures of the different configurations of the energy system in Portugal (outputs of the Calliope model and inputs to the ENBIOS tool) to their LCA impacts through Monte Carlo simulations. Additionally, we assess the sensitivity of the model through Spearman correlation. This is a part of the performed analyses, which include sensitivity auditing (SAUD) (Saltelli and Funtowicz 2014) and pedigree matrixes from NUSAP (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1990), which can be found in de Tomás-Pascual et al. (2024).

METHODS

The SEEDS workflow

The human-computer loop performed in SEEDS started with an action-research guided engagement process to identify key parameters to be included in energy and environmental modelling (Campos et al. 2024; Firmino De Souza et al. 2022). Then, we calculated configurations of energy transition in Portugal with the Calliope framework, considering a set of techno-economic suboptimal options. This analysis resulted in 270 pathways that were assessed with the ENBIOS tool to calculate their socio-environmental impacts. Calliope and ENBIOS are soft-linked through Calliope outputs of energy production per technology type. The results are shown in a webapp that is the project's flagship, and which is designed as a tool to support public decision-making. We included a qualitative assessment of uncertainty in the SEEDS webapp for stakeholders to understand the functioning and the model and some general uncertainty issues, detailed in de Tomás-Pascual et al. (2024).

Calliope

The energy system of Portugal is modelled with the open-source framework Calliope (Pfenninger & Pickering, 2018), which allows to explore different regional and technological configurations of highly renewable energy systems. In particular, we build on the existing Sector-Coupled Euro-Calliope (SC-EC) model generator (Pickering, Lombardi, and Pfenninger 2022; Pickering 2022). These are Calliope-interpretable model datasets for any European country, including all energy sectors and several sub-national regions for renewables deployment. The specific modelling approach used here allows for the exploration of a diversity of maximally different system designs within 10% of the lowest cost. These designs are called SPORES, after the name of the algorithm used to generate them, which belongs to the family of Modelling to Generate Alternatives (MGA) algorithms. Having this number of possible solutions, we decrease the inherent uncertainty of a single optimal solution. However, there are assumptions and modelling choices that affect uncertainty such as the assessment of one only point in time instead of a whole transition, or the difficulty to estimate costs of future technologies. The technologies included in Euro-Calliope are low-carbon and renewable. Therefore, GHG emissions are not included in the cost-optimization function. In this work, we show 2 environmental impacts calculated with ENBIOS and our objective here is to identify what technologies make a given configuration higher impacting than others.

ENBIOS

We used the open-source tool ENBIOS (Soleymani-Fard et al. 2023) for the calculation of the environmental impacts. This python package integrates Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Multi-Scale Integrated Analysis of Societal and Ecosystem Metabolism (MuSIASEM) described in Madrid-López (2021). For more details on the methods to assess the uncertainty in ENBIOS, see de Tomás-Pascual et al. (de Tomás-Pascual et al. 2023). The results offer a holistic understanding of the socioenvironmental implications associated with different energy transition configurations with a hierarchical structure, as shown in the dendrogram in Figure 1.

We used data on resource use and emissions for each technology in the form of life cycle inventories from Ecoinvent 3.9.1 (Wernet et al. 2016). Life cycle inventories are very detailed datasets that register the inputs and emissions associated to the production of one unit of a certain output, such as energy carriers (in kWh) or other reference flows such as batteries (in kg). Input and emissions in inventories do not only refer to the operation of the energy technology, but also cover direct and indirect inputs and emissions. Inventory datasets are based on assumptions and average data and result in accumulated uncertainties. For example, the modelling choices about the lifetime and overall production

of devices and machinery, the detail of the production chains (boundaries of the system) or the type of device (referring to a similar technology of what we are expecting or to old, outdated data), they all have an impact in the results. It is a decision of the modeller to select the most similar or representative processes to those in the analysed system and can also make adaptations. In this sense, there is another inherent uncertainty of exploration of possible futures: we do not really know how technology will be in the future. In this work, however, we are using data from existing technologies to avoid the uncertainty related to prospective analysis.

For the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA), we use midpoint indicators from the ReCiPe 2016 v1.03 method (Huijbregts et al. 2017), with a hierarchical perspective that considers the mid-term impacts. LCIA also entails uncertainty and is based in some assumptions, such as linearity, overlooking the possible higher marginal impacts of emissions at surpassing certain thresholds (Raynolds, Checkel, and Fraser 1999; Pizzol et al. 2020). In this paper, we focus on 2 impact indicators: agricultural land occupation (LOP) and water consumption potential (WCP).

Figure 1 Dendrogram of the energy system under analysis, showing the hierarchical representation at different levels. The level n-3 is linked to Life Cycle Inventories.

RESULTS

Spearman correlation (level n-3)

Spearman rank correlation coefficients determine the influence of the input data (here, the energy mix at level n-3) on the output distribution (environmental impacts) (Groen et al. 2017; Saltelli and Marivoet 1990). We examined the relation between the input values (energy mix) and both impact indicators to understand the correlation between technologies and impacts. This also helps with the identification of the hotspot technologies whose inventories could be replaced by an alternative if it is considered that their uncertainty might be a key influencing factor in the model output. We computed the Spearman correlation values in python using SciPy (Virtanen et al. 2020). The sensitivity related to the “*open_field_pv*” technology appears as one of the highest contributors to all the impact categories (ρ between 0.9 to 0.92) followed by pumped hydro (ρ between 0.79 to 0.8) and electrolysis (ρ between 0.54 to 0.75). Conversely, *wind_onshore* occurs to be negatively correlated to the total impact observed in the different categories (ρ between -0.67 to -0.83) followed by *biofuel_to_methane* (ρ between -0.56 to -0.72).

Figure 2 Spearman correlation values between impact categories (level n) and input technology (TWh) (level n-3)

Monte Carlo

In order to assess the accumulated uncertainty in the LCA, we conducted Monte Carlo simulations consisting of 100 iterations focusing on a single spore. As shown in Figure 3, the error associated with this individual configuration spans from 0.97 to 1.2 times the environmental impact indicated by the deterministic result.

Figure 3 Water consumption potential impacts for 271 energy system configurations (spores). The results are normalized by the selected spore. The blue violin indicates the density distribution of spores. The red line highlights the error calculated from the standard deviation and mean of the stochastic values of the selected spore using Monte Carlo.

DISCUSSION

The model output indicates that open-field solar electricity production, pumped hydro, and electrolysis show high sensitivity. On the other hand, wind onshore and biofuel to methane display a negative correlation with the model output impacts. This result appears counterintuitive when viewed from a life cycle assessment (LCA) perspective. As explained in de Tomás-Pascual et al. (2024) the distribution of different energy pathways accounts for these negative values. The negative correlation of wind onshore with the amount of solar PV can be explained by the fact that more wind onshore typically means less solar, which results in the negative Spearman correlation of this technology. While the same explanation applies to pumped hydro, the biofuel-to-methane result is explained by a negative correlation with electrolysis (see de Tomás-Pascual et al. (2024)).

Monte Carlo simulations have shown that there is a significant amount of uncertainty in the environmental impacts associated with a single configuration. This uncertainty arises due to the high level of inherent uncertainty in the LCA modelling process and the fact that only one solution is being considered. Modelling frameworks often fail to capture the full spectrum of uncertainties inherent in the real-world, particularly regarding the diversity of stakeholder perspectives and interests. By focusing on a single solution, these frameworks neglect the complexities and nuances of various equally feasible solutions. *Modelling to generate alternatives* frameworks address this uncertainty, generally referred to as structural uncertainty. This approach creates an option space – a dynamic array of alternatives—within which the decision-makers and stakeholders can navigate. This cloud of alternatives results in a second cloud of environmental impacts, which expands significantly when considering the uncertainty inherent in environmental models.

It is crucial to recognize and openly address these uncertainties in policymaking. Transparency and open communication of uncertainty are vital components of this process to ensure that stakeholders have the necessary information to make informed decisions (Saltelli and Funtowicz 2014).

CONCLUSIONS

Models are not forecasting tools. They are representations of systems: necessarily a simplification of reality. They allow us to explore possible futures but are full of assumptions and modelling choices due to technical limitations, values, and priorities. It is fundamental to acknowledge and represent their inherent uncertainty and sensitivity in order to limit risks. In this paper, we have examined the uncertainty of the SEEDS workflow, that comprises a participatory process, the Calliope energy optimization model and the ENBIOS environmental impact. The numerical assessment has been performed for the ENBIOS tool and the technological mix: the outputs of Calliope that are inputs to ENBIOS.

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REFERENCES

- Campos, Ines, Aías Santino, Guilherme Luz, Miguel Brito, and Luis Fazendeiro. 2024. “Multicriteria Framework Based on Expert Stakeholder Preferences. Deliverable 4.4 - SEEDS Project.”
- Firmino De Souza, Debora Conceição, Ilja Šmorgun, David Jose Ribeiro Lamas, Joanna Agata Rutkowska, Gabriela De Moraes Beltrão, Silvia Keerd, Girish Srinivas Rao Nalawade, and Yi-Ting Yeh. 2022. “D3.1. Report on the Background Research, Development of the Initial Design Concept and D3.2 Initial Design Concept, Personas and Scenarios - SEEDS Project.”
- Funtowicz, Silvio O., and Jerome R. Ravetz. 1990. *Uncertainty and Quality in Science for Policy*. Dordrecht, the Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-0621-1>.
- . 1993. “Science for the Post-Normal Age.” *Futures* 25 (7): 739–55. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287\(93\)90022-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0016-3287(93)90022-L).
- Groen, Evelyne A., Eddie A.M. Bokkers, Reinout Heijungs, and Imke J.M. de Boer. 2017. “Methods for Global Sensitivity Analysis in Life Cycle Assessment.” *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 22: 1125–37. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367->

016-1217-3.

- Huijbregts, Mark A.J., Zoran J.N. Steinmann, Pieter M.F. Elshout, Gea Stam, Francesca Verones, Marisa Vieira, Michiel Zijp, Anne Hollander, and Rosalie van Zelm. 2017. "ReCiPe2016: A Harmonised Life Cycle Impact Assessment Method at Midpoint and Endpoint Level." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 22 (2): 138–47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11367-016-1246-y>.
- Pickering, Bryn. 2022. "Diversity of Options to Eliminate Fossil Fuels and Reach Carbon-Neutrality across the Entire European Energy System (2022-05-13) [Data Set]." Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6546817>.
- Pickering, Bryn, Francesco Lombardi, and Stefan Pfenninger. 2022. "Diversity of Options to Eliminate Fossil Fuels and Reach Carbon Neutrality across the Entire European Energy System." *Joule* 6 (6): 1253–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2022.05.009>.
- Pizzol, Massimo, Romain Sacchi, Susanne Köhler, and Annika Anderson Erjavec. 2020. "Non-Linearity in the Life Cycle Assessment of Scalable and Emerging Technologies." *Frontiers in Sustainability* 1 (January): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2020.611593>.
- Raynolds, Marlo, M. D. Checkel, and R. A. Fraser. 1999. "Application of Monte Carlo Analysis to Life Cycle Assessment." *SAE Technical Papers* 108: 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4271/1999-01-0011>.
- Saltelli, Andrea, and Silvio Funtowicz. 2014. "When All Models Are Wrong." *Issues in Science and Technology* 30 (2): 79–85.
- Saltelli, Andrea, and J. Marivoet. 1990. "Non-Parametric Statistics in Sensitivity Analysis for Model Output: A Comparison of Selected Techniques." *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 28: 229–53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0951-8320\(90\)90065-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0951-8320(90)90065-U).
- "SEEDS: Stakeholder-Based Environmentally-Sustainable and Economically Doable Scenarios for the Energy Transition." n.d. <https://seeds-project.org/>.
- Soleymani-Fard, Ramin, Miquel Sierra, Alexander de Tomás-Pascual, and Cristina Madrid-López. 2023. "Enbios · PyPI." 2023. <https://pypi.org/project/enbios/>.
- Tomás-Pascual, Alexander de, Laura Pérez-Sánchez, Ramin Soleymani-Fard, Gara Villalba, and Cristina Madrid-López. 2024. "Quantification of Uncertainty Associated with Each Scenario across Multiple Dimensions. Deliverable 2.3. SEEDS Project."
- Tomás-Pascual, Alexander de, Miquel Sierra-Montoya, Rafael Nebot, Ramin Soleymani-Fard, Gara Villalba, and Cristina Madrid-López. 2023. "Socio-Environmental Metabolic Pattern and Associated Impacts of Energy System Scenarios. Deliverable 2.2. SEEDS Project (Version 1)." <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994038>.
- Virtanen, Pauli, Ralf Gommers, Travis E. Oliphant, Matt Haberland, Tyler Reddy, David Cournapeau, Evgeni Burovski, et al. 2020. "SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python." *Nature Methods* 17: 261–72. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2>.
- Wernet, G., C. Bauer, B. Steubing, J. Reinhard, E. Moreno-Ruiz, and B. Weidema. 2016. "The Ecoinvent Database Version 3 (Part I): Overview and Methodology." *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 21 (9): 1218–30. <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11367-016-1087-8>.